

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

Grant Agreement ID: 101091268

D5.10 Plan for dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy version 2

Project	NOVASOIL
Project title	INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH
Work Package	5
Deliverable	5.10
Period covered	01/11/2023-30/04/2024
Publication date	30/04/2024
Dissemination level	PU
Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this report	EVENOR
Authors	González-Peñaloza F, Alonso Martín F, Bravo-García J, Blanco-Velázquez FJ and Anaya-Romero M
Contributors	ALL

QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

Following the steps followed for the review of this deliverable can be found.

TABLE REVISION HISTORY DELIVERABLE

Row	Version	Date	Reviewers	Description
1	V1.0	07/04/2024	EVENOR	Draft version circulated
2	V1.1	29/04/2024	ALL	Inputs provided by consortium
3	V2.0	30/04/2024	EVENOR	Final version

Project Consortium

N°	Participant organisation name	Country
1	EVENOR TECH SLU	ES
2	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG	GE
3	ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA	LV
4	NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY	BU
5	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
6	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	DK
7	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	GE
8	ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES	FR
9	ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL	IT
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	IT
11	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	NL
12	CENTRE OF ESTONIAN RURAL RESEARCH AND KNOWLEDGE	EE
13	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	ES
14	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	IT
15	ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA	ES
16	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	GB

Table of contents

1	Summary.....	6
2	Introduction	6
	Document updating.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
	Dissemination activities held	12
	Objectives.....	19
	Prediction Model.....	24
	Normalization and Exploratory Data Analysis.....	25
	Visits by countries	28
	Social Media.....	32
	Post.....	33
	Insights and Recommendations	35
	SWOT analysis.....	35
	Strengths:	35
	Weaknesses:	36
	Opportunities:.....	36
	Threats:.....	36
	Challenges and Lessons Learned.....	36
3	Conclusion.....	38
4	Appendix	40
5	Acknowledgment.....	46

1 Summary

The NOVASOIL project, funded by the European Union under a grant agreement 101091268, represents an unprecedented collaborative effort to innovate business models for soil health. The project brings together a diverse consortium of 16 organizations from across Europe, including universities, research institutes and agricultural associations, with the common goal of developing, implementing and disseminating sustainable business models and agricultural practices that promote soil health.

The report details the initial phases of the project, from quality assurance procedures to statistical analysis of website engagement, predictive modelling of future engagement and geographical engagement analysis. Through the project platform, NOVASOIL has managed to establish a solid base of interested users, as evidenced by an analysis of sessions on the website, which shows moderate but consistent engagement, with significant variations that offer opportunities to adapt and improve the participation strategy.

Geographical segmentation of site visits shows a diverse user base, with Spain, Italy, Germany, Belgium and the Netherlands leading in sessions. This analysis provides crucial information for future content and marketing strategies, allowing the NOVASOIL project to better adapt to the needs and preferences of its audience.

In addition, the project has established a significant social media presence, using platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn to engage with its audience. A detailed analysis of social media activity identifies opportunities to increase engagement and visibility of the project.

This report serves as a testament to the initial progress and potential impact of the NOVASOIL project. As we move forward, we are committed to continuing to research and develop innovative solutions for soil health, which is critical to long-term agricultural sustainability and environmental well-being.

2 Introduction

To tackle the global challenge of agricultural sustainability and soil health, we need innovative and committed responses. The NOVASOIL project, funded by the European Union under grant agreement 101091268, aims to promote sustainable agricultural business models. The project's goal is to preserve soil vitality for future generations. NOVASOIL is a collaborative effort between 16 leading agricultural research, education, and practice organizations in Europe. The project

aims to address a pressing environmental issue through interdisciplinary and cross-border collaboration.

The project has achieved impressive initial results, reflecting the growing interest and participation of the global community. Analysis of sessions on the project website indicates a high level of engagement. The daily average of sessions shows that visitors are interested in learning more about sustainable practices and the project's work. Spikes in activity reinforce this engagement, highlighting the relevance of published content and dissemination campaigns. These findings demonstrate a clear impact on raising awareness of soil health.

The social media strategy of the NOVASOIL project has effectively fostered an engaged community and promoted open dialogue on agricultural sustainability. The NOVASOIL project has a presence on social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. This has resulted in sustained growth in followers and an interaction rate that exceeds initial expectations. The success of the project reflects the growing interest in sustainability and soil health issues. Our communication and dissemination strategies have been effective in achieving these positive results.

This text demonstrates the project's potential to influence public perception and encourage significant change towards more sustainable agricultural practices. It also serves as a clear call to action, encouraging more people to join our cause and contribute to the legacy of a more sustainable planet.

Moving forward, we are committed to deepening our mission. We are motivated by these initial results and believe that together we can make a tangible difference in the world. The NOVASOIL project is an innovative initiative that prioritizes soil health and agricultural sustainability on the global agenda.

According to the results, the NOVASOIL project has effectively integrated digital marketing tools into its dissemination processes, reflecting a modern and effective strategy to increase the reach and impact of its research and objectives. Based on the information provided in the document and the importance of these tools, here are some reasons why the use of social networks and web analytics is a useful and correct practice for the dissemination of the project:

1. Widening the scope

Social media and the NOVASOIL project website act as direct channels to extend the reach of the project to a global audience. The ability of these platforms to connect with interested individuals and organizations around the world is unparalleled. This is particularly

7

important for a project that addresses global issues such as soil health and agricultural sustainability, issues that require collective attention and action.

2. Interaction and engagement

The real-time interaction offered by social media provides an invaluable platform for community engagement and participation. Through comments, likes, shares and direct dialogue, the NOVASOIL project can gather feedback, answer questions and foster an active and engaged community. This continuous feedback is essential to adapt and improve the dissemination strategies and content of the project.

3. Effective segmentation

Digital marketing allows for highly effective segmentation, ensuring that the NOVASOIL project's content and messages reach the most relevant audiences. Using advanced analytical tools, the project can identify the trends, interests and demographics of its audience, allowing for the personalization of content to maximize interest and engagement.

4. Analysis and measurement

Digital platforms offer robust analytical tools that allow the impact and effectiveness of dissemination strategies to be measured in real time. By analyzing key metrics such as web traffic, interaction rates, follower growth and conversions, the NOVASOIL project can adjust its tactics to optimize results and ensure the efficient and effective dissemination of its content.

5. Cost-effectiveness

Compared to traditional dissemination methods, digital marketing tools offer a cost-effective solution for the NOVASOIL project. With limited budgets, the ability to reach a global audience, engage with stakeholders and accurately measure impact, all at a relatively low cost, is a significant advantage.

6. Dynamic and versatile content

The use of digital platforms allows for the creation and distribution of dynamic and versatile content, from blog posts and in-depth articles to videos, infographics and podcasts. This variety of content formats not only enriches the user experience, but also allows information to be presented in a more accessible and engaging way to different audiences.

Updates from D5.5

The update of the NOVASOIL project content documents shows a significant evolution in the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies from the first version to the latest one. We have tried to make the updates reflect a more detailed and structured approach, incorporating more rigorous quality assurance procedures, expanding communication tactics through the use of digital technologies and social media, and emphasizing privacy and the proper handling of information. There is also more detail in the planning of dissemination events and a clearer definition of the responsibilities of consortium members. These changes reflect a stronger commitment to increasing the visibility and impact of the project, ensuring that the innovations and results achieved effectively reach a wider and more diverse audience.

Below are the main changes and updates we found between the first version and the current version of the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy Plan¹:

Quality assurance procedures

The updated version specifies in more detail the procedures followed for the review of the document, reflecting a more structured methodology compared to the previous version, which emphasised following the general guidelines of the European Commission.

Communication and dissemination strategies

The updated version has expanded and detailed the communication and dissemination strategies and materials, such as the inclusion of PowerPoint templates and the use of social media and online events to reach a wider audience, which was not as detailed in the first version.

Multiplication events and activities

There is a new inclusion of multiplication events in the updated version, highlighting more proactive planning and participation in relevant events to increase the visibility and impact of the project. This includes details of how and when these events will take place.

Focus on data protection and information management

The updated version includes additional details on confidentiality and information handling rules to ensure compliance with GDPR and other data protection standards, which is addressed more generally in the original version.

¹ The latest version (D5.10) includes newer updates with revision dates up to 04/30/2024, while the initial version (D5.5) has the latest revision date of 04/28/2023.

Enlargement and details of consortium participation

The list of consortium members and their role in the project has remained fairly consistent, but the updated version provides more clarity on members' responsibilities and specific involvement in various project activities.

Advances on the NOVASOIL web

With the launch of the updated NOVASOIL project web portal, we have introduced a significant improvement, such as a landing page dedicated exclusively to highlighting the dissemination activities of our project. This innovation aims not only to improve the accessibility and dissemination of key information to those interested in the project's processes, activities and development, but also to encourage greater participation and engagement. The structure of the site, organized through intuitive tabs, provides direct access to a wide range of resources: public deliverables, audiovisual material, factsheets and detailed information on upcoming and ongoing events.

This landing page has been carefully designed to serve as the epicenter of our dissemination activities, highlighting the benefits of our project. By providing a platform where information is easily accessible and well organized, we aim to equip our users with the knowledge they need to fully understand and actively participate in the project. This approach not only ensures that essential information is consulted efficiently, but also enriches the user experience of browsing our site, fostering a community that is better informed, more connected and more committed to our common goal.

ABOUT

SISTER PROJECTS

WORK PACKAGES

DISSEMINATION

PARTNERS

INTRANET

IN PRESS

CONTACT

LOGIN

Dissemination

Deliverables Videos Factsheet Events

Events held

NOVASOIL Online Event: Soil Health for a Sustainable Future (Tuesday, 12 December)

Show **10** entries Search:

Title	Speaker	Download
Innovative Business Models For Soil Health (NOVASOIL)FOR SOIL HEALTH (NOVASOIL)	MSc Francisco José Blanco-Velazquez	
The CO2-Land association's programme for climate and soil protection through humus formation	Dr. Karl Müller-Sämann,	
Case NL: Business Models for Carbon Farming	Liesbeth Dries	
Needs and demands identified	MSc Francisco José Blanco-Velazquez	

Figure 1. Landing page focusing on dissemination activities

In order to make it easy for members to upload information about their activities, a form has been developed where they can enter all the relevant information.

Members are asked to indicate on the form the activities they have carried out, are planning to carry out or have already carried out.

[ABOUT](#)[SISTER
PROJECTS](#)[WORK
PACKAGES](#)[DISSEMINATION](#)[PARTNERS](#)[INTRANET](#)[IN PRESS](#)[CONTACT](#)[LOGOUT](#)

Intranet

data-view-breakpoint-pointer="e8b5e14c-fa0c-4461-8854-c6dd8a3a962d" >

Upcoming Events

class="tribe-events-c-messages__message-list-item" data-key="0" > There are no upcoming events.

[Dissemination Activity Report Submission Form](#)

Dissemination Activity Report Submission Form

Dissemination Activity Report Submission Form

Date of the Event

mm/dd/yyyy

The specific date(s) when the activity occurred.

Location(Required)

Street Address

Address Line 2

City

State / Province / Region

Country

The geographical location or online platform where the activity took place.

Figure 2. Form for collecting information on dissemination activities.

Dissemination activities held

In this report, a list of the dissemination activities that have been carried out throughout this period of time will be made; However, it is noted that there will soon be document updates with the addition of new ones.

NOVASOIL Online Event: Soil Health for a Sustainable Future (Tuesday, 12 December) 🌻

The event comprehensively addressed soil health as a central axis for developing a sustainable future and brought together a diverse audience of more than 240 participants. This was made possible by an effective digital marketing strategy designed to reach a wide range of people interested in the topic. A key focus of the discussion was the identification and critical role of key stakeholders in the design and implementation of innovative business models that promote soil health. Particular emphasis was placed on organic farming practices and the need to raise public awareness of the critical importance of

maintaining and improving soil fertility as a challenge for society as a whole.

During the presentations and discussions, a variety of soil management practices were shared and explored, such as minimizing tillage, incorporating cover crops, implementing crop rotations and adopting agroforestry. These techniques were discussed as effective means of not only improving soil health but also increasing carbon sequestration, highlighting their relevance in the context of the current climate crisis.

Carbon farming was also explored from an innovative perspective, looking at business models beyond the traditional agri-food chain. One notable example was the opportunity for farmers to generate additional income by selling carbon credits to offset carbon emissions from industries not directly related to agriculture. This discussion highlighted the emergence of carbon markets as a relevant economic opportunity for the agricultural sector.

Finally, the event culminated in the launch of a Digital Knowledge Centre, an initiative designed to serve as a comprehensive resource for those interested in soil health. This center aims to provide access to up-to-date information on soil health business models, relevant policies, best practices and projects under development. The intention is to foster a vibrant and engaged community of practice that can share knowledge, experiences and solutions to common challenges in promoting soil health, thus becoming a pillar for progress towards sustainability in agriculture and land management.

Soil health and ecosystem services: emerging narratives and policy integration of incentive-based instruments

(23rd of June 2023)

The NOVASOIL project was presented at the 12th Conference of the AIEAA (Associazione Italiana di Economia Agraria e Applicata), held on 23 and 24 June. On this occasion, dedicated researchers from the University of Ferrara and the University of Pisa addressed key aspects of promoting soil health through ecosystem services, bringing together extensive experience to drive this transformative initiative forward.

The presentation began with a thoughtful introduction that immersed participants in the heart of NOVASOIL's mission. Each participant was reminded of the integral role that soils play in maintaining and enhancing terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems and the well-being of all the species that inhabit them.

The symposium explored the intersection of narrative and policy, analysing how the narratives of policy makers shape the trajectory of

agricultural practices. The regulatory framework for soil protection in the EU became a saga, highlighting the need to balance economic objectives, social considerations and environmental sustainability.

In an intellectually challenging dialogue, participants addressed complex technical challenges and aspirations. The discourse moved from the limits of awareness to comprehensive educational strategies to ensure a deep understanding of the economic, social and environmental aspects of sustainable land management.

The presentation concluded with questions from participants and a sense of purpose to promote sustainable soil ecosystems. At this meeting, the NOVASOIL project emphasised that promoting soil health is not just a scientific endeavour, but a collective commitment to responsible land management.

Modelli di business innovativi per la salute del suolo.

(25th of January 2024) 🌸

The sessions dedicated to the NOVASOIL project on 25 January 2024 were structured around several key activities aimed at highlighting and discussing the importance and applicability of innovative practices in soil health. Here is a more detailed description of each segment of the event:

- **Project Presentation:** This section presented the NOVASOIL project, its funding under the Horizon Europe programme and its main objective of promoting soil health through innovative business models. It highlights how such practices can benefit both society and the environment.
- **Description of activities and incentives:** Following the introduction, the specific activities and incentives planned within the project were described in detail. This included a description of how different business models could be used to improve soil health and how these models could be both economically and environmentally sustainable.
- **Discussion session:** During this part of the event, participants had the opportunity to discuss the presentations and to go deeper into specific topics. This session facilitated the exchange of ideas and experiences between the different partners and participants in the project.
- **Case studies presented**
 - **University of Pisa:** Two case studies were presented:
 - **PIF Flora Aromatica Santa Luce and La Valle Dei Profumi:** A project using a multifunctional and sustainable development model for marginal areas,

integrating aromatic and medicinal plant cultivation systems to improve biodiversity and soil health.

- Centro di Ricerche Agro-Ambientali "Enrico Avanzi": Long-term research on conventional, conservative and organic farming methods to assess their impact on soil health and agricultural production.
- University of Ferrara and Delta Institute (IDECO): Presented a case study on the Po Delta, Distretto delle Sabbie, showing how orthocultural production certification and carbon farming practices can play a crucial role in improving soil health and sustainable agricultural production.

Modelli di business innovativi per la salute del suolo.

(31 th of January 2024) 🌸

On 31st January the second edition of the conference dedicated to the NOVASOIL project took place, repeating the original event of 25th January. This new session was organised under the auspices of the European Union's Horizon Europe programme, with the aim of continuing to explore and promote soil health through innovative business models. These sessions continued to focus on understanding the environmental and social benefits of investing in practices that improve soil health.

The structure of the event maintained the successful format of the previous session, including

- Project presentation: The NOVASOIL project was reintroduced, highlighting its funding and main objectives.
- Description of activities and incentives: A detailed description of the planned activities within the project was offered, as well as the associated incentives for participants and stakeholders.
- Extended discussion session: Similar to the first day, this session allowed for an in-depth exchange of ideas and experiences among participants, fostering a constructive dialogue on sustainable business models in soil health.
- In addition, case studies were again presented by institutions such as the University of Pisa and the University of Ferrara, providing concrete examples of

- Multifunctional and sustainable development of marginal areas through the integration of innovative farming systems.
- Long-term research into farming methods to assess their impact on soil health and the effectiveness of sustainable farming practices.
- These days reaffirmed the importance of inter-institutional cooperation and innovation in land management, inspiring

participants to consider and adopt new practices that benefit both the environment and society.

Caso studio suoli sabbiosi del Delta del Po, un bene pubblico da salvaguardare.

(8th of February 2024) 🌸

The activities developed in the Novasoil project, carried out by the University of Pisa, the Istituto Delta Ecologia Applicata and the Università di Scienze Chimiche, Farmaceutiche ed Agrarie, focused on the implementation of sustainable agricultural practices aimed at improving and maintaining soil health in different regions of Italy. A summary of these activities is given below (Figure 3):

Multifunctional and sustainable development of marginal areas in Pisa: This initiative, led by the University of Pisa, focused on the province of Pisa in Tuscany. The activity introduced perennial aromatic crops, such as lavender, with the aim of improving soil health and biodiversity and developing a resilient value chain in previously marginalised areas.

Long-term trials at the University of Pisa: Conducted at the University of Pisa's Enrico Avanzi Agro-Environmental Research Centre, these studies evaluate practices such as direct seeding and crop rotation. The focus was on measuring the impact of these practices on soil conservation, biodiversity and agricultural productivity.

Conservation of sandy soils in the Po Delta: This activity was led by the Istituto Delta Ecologia Applicata and the University of Ferrara. It focused on the challenges and benefits of the sandy soils of the Po Delta, with the aim of improving the management of these soils to promote environmental, social and economic sustainability.

Figure 3. Screenshots of the presentations for the Italian activities

Innovative business models for soil health (NOVASOIL). Strategies for profitable and measurable soil health business models.

(6-7th of March 2024) 🌸

The ESA Symposium on Earth Observation for Soil Protection and Restoration served as the backdrop for the presentation of the

NOVASOIL project, led by Francisco José Blanco-Velázquez together with his team from EVENOR-TECH SLU (Spain), which aims to innovate business models for soil health. NOVASOIL, which runs from November 2022 to October 2025 and involves 16 partners in 10 countries with 17 case studies, focuses on developing a diverse portfolio of business cases and good examples for investing in soil health in Europe and beyond. Its objectives range from analyzing current models for creating new incentives and rents from healthy soils, implementing a co-development approach to promoting soil health, developing an incentive toolbox and testing network, to examining policies and current technologies that generate income for farmers and landowners. In addition, NOVASOIL aims to develop a community of practice around soil health investors and key stakeholders, and to raise awareness of soil health through a digital marketing strategy. Earth observation plays a crucial role in this project, particularly in the monitoring of environmental variables such as vegetation indices, water stress and soil organic carbon, which includes baseline establishment, validation, monitoring and verification using tools such as Google Earth Engine and ESA-linked services. This approach not only highlights the importance of advanced technologies in promoting soil health, but also raises fundamental questions about business model preferences, willingness to engage in carbon farming and the necessary technological support. In conclusion, NOVASOIL stands out as a collaborative effort towards innovation in soil management, promoting soil health not only as a scientific challenge, but as a collective commitment to responsible and sustainable soil management, demonstrating the importance of innovative, profitable and measurable business models for the future of sustainable agriculture.

Figure 4. Image with the presentation of the ESA conferences. Source: <https://www.eo4soilprotection.org>

General Assembly Thessaloniki, Central Macedonia.

(21th of March 2024) 🌸

The Assembly of European Horticultural Regions (AREFLH) is at the forefront of promoting sustainable agricultural practices across Europe and the NOVASOIL project, supported by the Horizon Europe program, is an outstanding initiative. During the General Assembly on 21 March in Thessaloniki, Greece, hosted by the Region of Central Macedonia, NOVASOIL was presented to stakeholders, policy makers, producer organizations and agricultural professionals. The event aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the project's objectives, which focus on the development of innovative business models to improve soil health. This session was crucial in fostering future collaborations and adapting the project's objectives to the diverse needs of European communities. AREFLH also took the opportunity to invite participants to join the Community of Practices (CoP) and announced this year's annual CoP event.

NOVASOIL is not an isolated effort, but part of AREFLH's broader strategy to integrate sustainable practices into all aspects of agriculture. It aligns with other initiatives such as SMARTPROTECT and Waste4Soil, which also aim to improve agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability through innovation. By demonstrating how NOVASOIL complements these projects, AREFLH presents a coherent approach to tackling the pressing challenges of modern agriculture. This project exemplifies AREFLH's innovative spirit and commitment to promoting sustainable agriculture by focusing on soil health to not only improve agricultural production, but also to ensure that these practices are beneficial to ecosystems. The knowledge and methods developed through NOVASOIL have the potential to inspire similar initiatives worldwide, positioning it as a model for sustainable agricultural practices.

Figure 1. AREFLH Activity Report 2023. Source: <https://www.areflh.org/en/?view=article&id=1548&catid=171>

The 13th AIEAA Conference "The social sustainability of European agriculture facing old and new challenges. Issues, methods and policies". Forthcoming activities 🍅
(20-21th June 2024)

15th IFSA Conference on systemic change for sustainable futures. held in Trapani (Sicily). Forthcoming activities 🍅
(30th June to 4th July 2024)

Objectives

Main objective

To comprehensively evaluate the progress and effectiveness of the dissemination strategies and tools implemented by the NOVASOIL project in order to maximize the impact and reach of its research and

results on soil health and sustainable agricultural practices, and to identify areas of success and areas for improvement in order to optimize future dissemination activities.

Specific objectives

- Analyse web engagement: Examine in detail the engagement metrics on the NOVASOIL project website, including traffic analysis, session duration and bounce rates, to better understand visitor behaviour and interest.
- Evaluation of social media presence: Analyse the effectiveness of the social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) used by NOVASOIL in terms of follower growth, levels of interaction and engagement, and quality of interactions to identify patterns of success and areas for further audience activation.
- Measure geographic reach: Breaking down and evaluating the geographic distribution of interactions with the project's website and social networks, identifying key markets and regions with growth potential to direct more focused outreach efforts.
- Content analysis: Review the effectiveness of content published on both the website and social networks, assessing its alignment with audience interests, thematic relevance and impact on engagement and knowledge dissemination.
- Identify improvements to digital tools: Based on the previous analyses, identify opportunities for improvement in the use of digital tools for dissemination, including recommendations for optimizing website design, content strategies on social networks and the implementation of new tools or emerging platforms.
- Engagement strategy: Based on data analysis, develop recommendations for more effective engagement strategies that can increase active audience participation and strengthen the online community around the NOVASOIL project.
- Future planning: Based on the findings and analysis of the document, propose a strategic plan for future dissemination activities to ensure that the NOVASOIL project continues to build on its successes and proactively addresses any identified challenges.
- Encourage Active Participation of Stakeholders in the NOVASOIL Project: Establish and deepen dialogue with a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, government

entities, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and the scientific community, to gather and understand their needs, realities and opinions. This will be achieved through the strategies:

- Creation of Discussion Forums: Implement online discussion forums on the NOVASOIL website to provide a space where stakeholders can share experiences, challenges and solutions related to soil health and agricultural sustainability.
- Surveys and Direct Feedback: Design and implement specific surveys aimed at different groups of stakeholders to collect their opinions and needs. This information will be crucial to adapt the project activities and ensure that they respond to the real needs of the field.
- Webinars and Thematic Workshops: Organize webinars and online workshops focused on key topics identified by stakeholders as of interest or concern. These events will serve as platforms for knowledge exchange and to encourage active community participation in the development of innovative solutions.
- Targeted Dissemination Campaigns: Use the data collected on the needs and realities of stakeholders to design more personalized and effective communication and dissemination campaigns, ensuring that the message of the NOVASOIL project reaches in a more resonant and meaningful way.
- Collaborative Content Development: Invite stakeholders to contribute content to the project website and social media, allowing their voices and perspectives to be highlighted and shared with a broader audience.
- Virtual Collaboration Platform: Establish a virtual collaboration platform that facilitates the co-creation of projects, the presentation of innovative proposals and the joint development of practical solutions for identified challenges, thus fostering a sense of ownership and commitment to the objectives of the NOVASOIL project.

By incorporating this objective in the document, NOVASOIL will be able to not only expand its impact but also enrich its knowledge base and intervention strategies with the valuable contributions of a diverse and committed community of stakeholders. This two-way communication and collaboration strategy ensures that the project remains relevant, adaptive, and aligned with the emerging needs of the field of soil health and agricultural sustainability.

Sessions vs Date

Figure 5. Evolution of visits to the site by time of existence. Source: Google Analytics

Table 1. Statistical summary with visits to the NOVASOIL website. Source: Google Analytics

Statistic	Value
Mean Sessions per Day	23.03
Standard Deviation	34.32
Minimum Sessions	1
Maximum Sessions	573
Median Sessions	16

The statistical summary of the NOVASOIL project website sessions offers several key insights into user engagement over the observed period:

- **Average Daily Activity:** The mean sessions per day standing at 23.03 indicates a moderate level of daily user engagement on the website. This suggests that on average, the site attracts a consistent number of visitors daily.
- **Variability in User Engagement:** A standard deviation of 34.32 points to a high variability in daily sessions. This high fluctuation suggests that user engagement with the website is not consistent day-to-day but rather varies significantly. Some days may see exceptionally high activity, while others are much quieter.

- **Range of Sessions:** The minimum and maximum sessions recorded (1 and 573, respectively) show an extensive range of user activity levels. The minimum value highlights days with very low engagement, which could be due to various factors like technical issues, lack of new content, or simply normal fluctuations in user interest. Conversely, the maximum sessions value indicates days when the website experienced exceptionally high traffic, possibly driven by marketing efforts, new content releases, or external events attracting users.
- **Median Sessions:** The median sessions value of 16, being lower than the mean, suggests that the distribution of daily sessions is skewed towards lower activity levels for the majority of days. However, the presence of days with very high session counts (outliers) pulls the mean above the median, highlighting those occasional spikes in activity.

These statistics together paint a picture of a website with a base level of consistent user interest, punctuated by periods of significantly higher engagement. Understanding the drivers behind these peaks could be valuable for strategic planning, content scheduling, or marketing efforts to enhance user engagement further. It might also be useful to examine the correlation of these spikes with specific events or content releases to better understand user behavior and preferences.

The trend of weekly average sessions on the NOVASOIL project website reveals how user engagement has evolved over time. The plot shows the average number of sessions per week, offering a smoother view of trends by reducing the impact of day-to-day fluctuations.

Key observations from the trend might include:

- **Periods of Increased Engagement:** Peaks in the graph indicate weeks where the website experienced higher than average user sessions. These could correlate with specific events, such as marketing campaigns, new content releases, or external factors driving interest to the site.
- **Stability or Variability:** The overall trend line provides insights into whether user engagement has been stable, increasing, or decreasing over the observed period. A stable line would suggest consistent interest, whereas a visible upward or downward trend could indicate growing or waning user engagement, respectively.
- **Seasonal Patterns or Anomalies:** Any recurring patterns in the data might suggest seasonal trends in user engagement, which could be crucial for planning future content or marketing strategies.

This visual trend analysis offers a foundation for deeper exploration into what drives engagement on the NOVASOIL project website, aiding in strategic decisions to enhance user interaction.

handling time series that present complex trends and seasonalities, as well as its robustness to incomplete data and its accessible operability.

The choice of Prophet, developed by Facebook, as a predictive analysis tool is justified by its intrinsic ability to disaggregate time series components into trends, seasonalities and holiday effects, which makes the model especially suitable for forecasts with a high degree of complexity. In addition, Prophet is distinguished by its flexibility and its ability to handle irregularities in data, thus providing reliable and easily interpretable forecasts, which is vital to support data-driven decision making.

Normalization and Exploratory Data Analysis

Data Preparation

The dataset, commencing on the 1st of December 2022, encompassed 458 records of daily sessions on the NOVASOIL project's website. To align with Prophet's requirements, the data underwent a transformation where the date column was designated as 'ds' and the sessions column as 'y'.

Exploratory Analysis

Subsequent examination revealed an average of 23 sessions per day, with a pronounced variability ranging from a minimum of 1 to a maximum of 573 sessions daily. Additionally, the median daily session count was observed to be 16, signifying that the majority of days had session counts below the average, thus pointing to a skewed distribution with occasional peaks in user engagement.

Figure 7. Dataset and model

The **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** shows both historical data and future predictions for the sessions on the NOVASOIL project website, where we can provide your information:

- Black dots: represent the actual historical session data by date (d_s on the horizontal axis and y on the vertical axis).
- Blue line: Indicates the central tendency of the model forecast; this is the forecast line (\hat{y}) generated by Prophet.
- Light blue band: Reflects the uncertainty interval of the predictions. That is, \hat{y}_{lower} and \hat{y}_{upper} indicate the range within which the model predicts the actual values will fall with a given probability (usually a 95% confidence interval).

According to the model, there is significant variation in the historical data, as shown by scattered values and some outliers that are quite far from the majority of data points (for example, points that are over 200 sessions).

The central trend line indicates the general direction in which the model expects sessions to move in the future.

The uncertainty band increases as we move further into the future, indicating that there is more uncertainty in the predictions as the time horizon extends.

The overall trend appears relatively flat, indicating that the model does not predict a significant change in the number of sessions over time.

It should be noted that as we approach the right-hand side of the graph (future dates), the predictions become less certain, as indicated by the

widening of the uncertainty band.

Figure 2

Figure 8.

. three separate components of a time series model

The figure shows three separate components of a time series model, likely generated by Prophet. These components are the general trend over time, weekly seasonality, and annual seasonality. Here is the interpretation of each one:

Trend (Top): The first graph shows a downward trend line over time in website sessions. The trend begins around February 2022 and projects through February 2025. The decreasing blue line suggests that the Prophet model is detecting an overall decrease in sessions over time, which may be a sign of declining interest or need to review user engagement strategies.

Weekly Seasonality (Medium): The second graph shows how the sessions vary depending on the day of the week. There appears to be a pattern where certain days of the week (Wednesday and Thursday, for example) have a positive influence on sessions, indicating that there are more sessions on those days compared to other days of the week (such as Saturdays), where the line drops significantly, indicating fewer sessions.

Annual Seasonality (Lower): The third graph shows the seasonality throughout the year. There are clear fluctuations that can be correlated to seasonal events or user behavior patterns throughout the year. For example, there may be spikes that coincide with specific events or seasons that naturally attract more interest. The line has risen and depressions that suggest more sessions at certain times of the year and fewer at others.

Visits by countries

Below is a breakdown of visits to the NOVASOIL website by country. As shown in the appendix, each row in the file lists a country along with the number of sessions that originated from that country, providing a clear view of the geographical distribution of website visitors. The data shows a diversity in the geographical origin of the sessions, with Spain leading the list with 2,233 sessions, followed by Italy, Germany, Belgium and the Netherlands with 1,119, 855, 766 and 706 sessions respectively. It is understood that this information could be invaluable in better understanding NOVASOIL's audience, allowing the company to adapt its marketing strategies, content and services to better serve its users in these regions. In addition, analyzing these sessions by country can help identify potential markets for expansion and areas where engagement and conversion efforts may need to be increased.

The analysis of visits to the NOVASOIL website from 1 November 2022 until one year later (*before the Plenary Meeting in Munich*) shows a geographical diversity of interactions, with a total of 6,698 sessions coming from 84 countries. However, the distribution of these visits shows considerable variability: while the average number of sessions per country is around 80, the median is only 10 sessions, indicating a concentration of activity in a few countries. This disparity becomes even more apparent when we consider that 25% of countries record 2 sessions or less, while the top 25% record 38 sessions or more. The country with the highest number of sessions is Spain, with 1,475, followed by Italy with 720, Germany with 617, Bulgaria with 542 and Belgium with 469, suggesting a strong platform presence in these markets. This pattern underlines the importance of these countries for NOVASOIL's global strategy, highlighting both growth

opportunities in well-established markets and the potential to expand into areas with lower penetration.

On the other hand, an analysis of visits to the NOVASOIL website from **1 November 2023 to 28 March 2024** shows a slightly different geographical interaction pattern compared to the previous year. During this last period, a total of 3,884 sessions from 77 different countries were recorded. The mean number of sessions per country was about 50, with a notable variability (a standard deviation of about 114 sessions), suggesting an even greater concentration of sessions in a few countries. The median was 7 sessions per country, meaning that more than half of the countries had 7 sessions or less, confirming the idea of a concentration of interest. The five countries with the highest number of sessions during this period were Spain with 759 sessions, Italy with 403, Belgium with 298, the Netherlands with 273 and France with 262. These results show a change in the distribution of sessions between countries compared to the previous period, with a significant decrease in the total number of sessions and a redistribution of contributions between countries.

The comparative analysis of the percentage of visits by country between the two periods shows significant variations in the interest and interaction of users with the NOVASOIL website. Here we highlight the countries with the largest increases and decreases in the percentage of visits:

Largest increases:

- United States: The percentage of visits increased by 2.27%, from 4.17% of the total to 6.44%.
- Portugal: The percentage of visits increased by 1.42%.
- Greece: Increased its percentage of visits by 1.17%.
- France: Increased its percentage of visits by 1.09%.
- Poland: Increased its percentage of visits by 0.90%.

Largest decreases:

- Bulgaria: Bulgaria's percentage of visits fell dramatically by 6.11%, from 8.09% to 1.98%.
- Germany: Experienced a 3.14% decrease in its percentage of visits.
- Spain: Although still the country with the highest percentage of visits, Spain experienced a 2.48% decrease in its participation.
- Peru: Its percentage of visits decreased by 0.98%.
- Mexico: Experienced a 0.46% decrease in its percentage of visits.

These changes in the percentage of visits by country may reflect a number of factors, including changes in the popularity of the NOVASOIL website in certain regions, the effectiveness of marketing strategies targeted at specific markets, or the evolution of the interests and needs of users in different countries. The sharp decline in countries such as Bulgaria and Germany, contrasted with increases in the United

States and Portugal, suggests a change in the geographical focus or resonance of the site with its international audience. This type of analysis can provide valuable information for adjusting content and marketing strategies to optimize overall reach and user engagement.

Sessions

The statistical analysis carried out to evaluate the differences in the number of sessions per country between two different periods for the Evenor Tech website was based on an independent samples test. This test is used to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between the means of two independent groups, in this case the before and after country sessions.

Independent samples t-test results:

- *t-value*: 1.11
- *p-value*: Approximately 0.27

Statistic	Value
Mean Before (NOV,2023)	110.12
Median Before (NOV,2023)	16.5
Mean After (NOV,2023)	63.98
Median After (NOV,2023)	16.5

<i>T-Statistic (NOV,2023)</i>	1.11
<i>P-Value (NOV,2023)</i>	0.27

The value obtained indicates the distance between the means of the two groups in terms of standard error. A higher t value indicates a greater difference between the groups. However, the associated *p-value* determines whether this difference is statistically significant. In this analysis, the p-value was about 0.27, which is above the generally accepted threshold of 0.05 for statistical significance. This means that there is not enough evidence to say that the differences observed in the means of sessions per country between the two periods are statistically significant.

The lack of statistically significant differences between the two periods suggests that the overall behavior of site visitors has not changed excessively in terms of the average number of sessions per country. This means that although there have been changes in the total number of visits or in the percentage participation of some countries, the variation in the average behavior per country is not enough to be considered statistically significant.

Although the test did not show significant differences in the means, the variability in the distribution of sessions, as seen in the box plots, suggests differences in the distribution of sessions between countries. This may be relevant for adjusting marketing strategies or country-specific content.

Despite the lack of significant changes in media, it may be useful to explore strategies to optimize the website and marketing campaigns, especially in countries where an increase or decrease in engagement was observed.

Focus on quality rather than quantity: Looking at the quality of sessions (e.g., session length, conversion rate) could provide additional insights into engagement and the effectiveness of content and marketing strategies.

Social Media

In today's digital age, where the media landscape is constantly evolving, brands and projects are looking to establish a strong and meaningful presence on social media. For the Novasoil Project, a pioneering initiative in its field, the digital marketing strategy is not only an extension of its identity, but also a crucial tool for building and maintaining a connection with its audience. Through a meticulous comparative analysis of your presence on the main social media platforms - Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn - we seek to unravel the dynamics of interaction, engagement and audience growth, providing valuable insights for future content and engagement strategies.

This report focuses on synthesizing and analyzing the Novasoil Project's activity between 1 November 2022 and 28 March 2024, highlighting how each platform uniquely contributes to the project's reach and resonance. By examining differences in follower growth, engagement rates and content effectiveness, we aim to provide a panoramic and specific view of the project's digital performance. In addition, emerging trends and best practices in digital marketing are considered to provide strategic recommendations that align future project actions with audience engagement and expansion goals.

In this context, the report will serve not only as a barometer of the Novasoil project's current social media success, but also as a compass for navigating the vast and sometimes unpredictable ocean of digital communications. Through this comparative analysis, we aim not only to evaluate, but also to inspire a digital marketing strategy that is both thoughtful and innovative, ensuring that the Novasoil Project continues to thrive in the digital ecosystem.

Post

Metric	Count	Mean	Std Dev	Min	25th Percentile	Median	75th Percentile	Max
Reactions	74	2.23	1.95	0	1	2	3.75	7
Comments	74	0.03	0.23	0	0	0	0	2
Shared times	74	0.5	0.73	0	0	0	1	3
Clicks	74	2.3	5.6	0	0	1	2	41
Impressions	74	48.72	29.48	6	30.5	40	56	174
Interaction Percentage	74	8.8%	7.06%	0%	3.69%	7.77%	13.83%	35%

Figure 3. Distribution of Social Media Publication Metrics

Delving into the analysis of Project Novasoil's posts, we offer a detailed report that closely examines the performance of the project's social media communications, focusing on key aspects such as visibility, engagement and audience interaction.

The Novasoil project produced 74 publications during the period analysed, achieving an average of 48.72 impressions per publication. This data reflects the project's ability to reach its audience, although it varies significantly between publications, with a maximum of 174 impressions and a minimum of only 6 impressions.

Audience engagement

- Reactions: On average, each post received approximately 2.23 reactions, indicating a moderate level of audience emotional engagement with the shared content.
- Comments: The average of 0.03 comments per post suggests limited conversational interaction, which could signal an opportunity to encourage more dialogue and direct engagement with the audience.
- Shares: With an average of 0.5 shares per post, there is potential to increase the redistribution of the project's content, thereby extending its reach and visibility.

Interaction and Participation

- Clicks: Posts generated an average of 2.3 clicks, indicating audience interest in further exploring the project's content or initiatives.

- Interaction Percentage: The average interaction rate was 8.80%, which suggests that there is room to optimize how content motivates the audience to interact.

Most and Least Effective Publications

- Most Viewed and Engaged: The December 14 post stood out in both visibility and engagement, with 174 impressions and an engagement rate of 10.92%. This post, focused on incentives for sustainable business models, resonated strongly with the audience.
- Least Viewed: The June 17 post, which had no description, was notably the least viewed with only 6 impressions, highlighting the importance of descriptive and engaging content.

Insights and Recommendations

- Enhance Conversational Interaction: Increase efforts to encourage comments and discussions, possibly through open questions or controversial topics that invite dialogue.
- Sharing Strategies: Analyze the content of the most frequently shared posts to identify patterns or themes that may encourage further redistribution.
- Content Optimization: Examine the characteristics of the most viewed and engaged posts to guide future content creation, focusing on high-interest topics, engaging visual formats, and clear calls to action.
- Timing Analysis: Evaluate posting times against engagement metrics to determine the most effective times to post and maximize visibility and engagement.

SWOT analysis

Creating a SWOT (Weaknesses, Threats, Strengths and Opportunities) analysis for the NOVASOIL project, based on the information provided in this document, can provide a clear view of your current situation and help guide future strategic decisions. Here is a preliminary SWOT analysis:

Strengths:

- Advanced web data analysis: Effective use of analytics tools to understand user behaviour and content effectiveness, enabling data-driven adjustments.
- Diversified social content: The ability to generate different content formats (articles, videos, infographics) to keep audiences interested and engaged.
- Sustainable online community growth: Successfully build a digital community around the project, demonstrating ongoing interest in its goals and outcomes.

- Geographical identification of users: Detailed analysis of the geographical origin of website visitors, enabling effective segmentation and personalisation of content.

Weaknesses:

- Dependence on external platforms: Vulnerable to changes in social media platform policies that may affect the visibility of content.
- Audience retention challenges: Difficulties in maintaining long-term audience interest and participation, especially given the abundance of digital content.
- Lack of direct interaction: Lack of spaces for direct interaction and dialogue with the community, which can limit the depth of engagement.

Opportunities:

- Adoption of new digital technologies: Experimenting with new technologies (augmented reality, chatbots) to enrich the user experience and provide innovative content.
- Working with influencers: Establish collaborations with sustainability influencers and opinion leaders to increase visibility and reach.
- Expand multilingual content: Develop and deliver content in multiple languages to attract and engage a broader and more diverse audience.
- Gamification initiatives: Implement gamification elements on the website and social media platforms to increase engagement and interactive learning.

Threats:

- Changes in digital consumer behavior: Adapting to the changing expectations and preferences of digital users who are looking for more meaningful and personalized interactions.
- Data security and privacy: Risks associated with the protection of personal data and user privacy, which can affect trust and participation.
- Increased competition in the digital space: The proliferation of similar projects and content vying for the attention of the same audience.
- Impact of external crises: Unforeseen global events (pandemics, economic crises) that can radically change online behavior and funding priorities.

Challenges and Lessons Learned

In the dynamic world of digital marketing, each project presents a unique set of challenges and learning opportunities. The NOVASOIL project, with its ambitious goal to innovate business models for soil

health and promote sustainable agricultural practices, was no exception. As we embark on this journey, we are faced with the task of not only communicating our mission, but also engaging and growing our online community in a meaningful way.

Throughout the development and implementation of our digital marketing strategy, we encountered several obstacles that tested our creativity, adaptability and resilience. These challenges ranged from the variability of web engagement and social media interaction to effective audience segmentation and measuring the return on investment of our digital campaigns. Each of these obstacles provided us with an opportunity to learn, adapt and improve.

This 'Challenges and Lessons Learned' section distils the essence of our experience, offering an introspective look at the difficulties we encountered and how we overcame them. By sharing these lessons, we hope to provide valuable insights that can benefit other projects with similar aspirations to bring about positive change through innovation in sustainability and agricultural practices. Here are the key challenges we faced on our digital journey and the key lessons we learned from each.

Variability in web participation

User engagement on the project website showed considerable variability, with peaks of activity followed by periods of low interaction. Conducting content analysis and making regular adjustments based on the data collected helped to identify the topics of greatest interest to the audience, allowing the publication schedule and content relevance to be optimized.

Limited interaction on social media

Despite sustained growth in follower numbers, actual engagement on social media platforms was initially low. By adopting a more interactive and participatory content strategy, including open-ended questions, polls and challenges, engagement increased significantly.

Difficulties in effective audience segmentation

Audience segmentation based on demographic and interest analysis did not initially deliver the expected results in terms of content personalisation. The integration of advanced web analytics tools and the tailoring of specific messages to identified audience segments led to a significant improvement in engagement and content relevance.

Adapting to the rapid pace of change in the digital environment

The digital environment is constantly evolving, with changes in social platform algorithms and the emergence of new trends. Adopting an agile approach to digital strategy planning, which allows for quick

adjustments and experimentation with new tactics, was essential to maintaining the relevance and scope of the project.

Ensuring the sustainability of your digital strategy

Maintaining the momentum of digital initiatives in the long term, especially after initial funding has ended, has been a challenge. Building collaborations with other organizations, using user-generated content and fostering an active community around the project emerged as key strategies to ensure sustainability.

3 Conclusion

The European Union-funded NOVASOIL project has reached an important milestone in promoting sustainable business models and agricultural practices that benefit soil health. Bringing together a consortium of 16 organisations from across Europe, the project has demonstrated its ability to build a solid foundation that promotes agricultural sustainability and soil conservation. By implementing effective digital strategies, including web analytics and social media presence, NOVASOIL has managed to attract and maintain a moderate but consistent level of user interest, identifying both initial successes and opportunities to adapt and improve the engagement strategy.

The use of web analytics and social media tools has enabled the project to extend its reach and tailor its messages to the needs of its audience. However, areas for improvement are identified, particularly in terms of audience retention and more direct interaction with the community. Creating more spaces for interaction and dialogue, as well as incorporating new digital technologies, could significantly improve the user experience and deepen their commitment to the project.

The challenges faced by NOVASOIL have provided valuable lessons in digital marketing and online community management, highlighting the importance of adaptability, continuous innovation and responding to user feedback to maintain long-term relevance and impact. In addition, the project has taken a new step forward, identifying key improvements and demonstrating the unwavering commitment of all consortium members to achieving the goals set. This collective commitment has been instrumental in overcoming obstacles and ensuring continued progress towards the mission of promoting sustainable agricultural practices and soil health.

Looking ahead, the project is well positioned to build on its initial successes and continue its commitment to innovation in soil health and agricultural sustainability. Optimising dissemination activities and deepening stakeholder engagement will be critical to seizing new

opportunities and addressing emerging challenges, thus ensuring maximum sustainability and long-term impact of the NOVASOIL project. NOVASOIL's trajectory to date reflects a successful combination of applied science, collaborative engagement and an effective communication strategy, which promises to continue moving towards a more sustainable agricultural future.

4 Appendix

Date	Hour	Message	Reactions	Comments	Shared times	Clicks	Impressions	Interaction percentage
Mar 26.	11:29	WORLD CLIMATE DAY. Time is of the essence. The weather is running out.	3	0	1	3	47	14,89 %
Mar 11.	09:14	ESA symposium explores Earth observation potential for soil protection \Dissemination activities\. https://ow.ly/JxL950QPW6r	2	0	0	19	60	35 %
Mar 08.	13:52	International Women's Day	2	0	0	0	36	5,56 %
Feb 23.	08:45	The concept and future prospects of soil health https://ow.ly/OIKT50QH1gi	4	2	1	13	117	17,09 %
Feb 16.	09:51	Report on Business Models and Social Innovations \Deliverable 2.2\ https://lnkd.in/eStqimqC	5	0	0	9	72	19,44 %
Feb 13.	18:09	Soil Organic Carbon Restoration through Organic Farming in Citrus Plantations Is sustainable farming worth your while ? https://ow.ly/VnMq50QAKmX	4	0	1	1	68	8,82 %
Dec 20.	13:43	Ready to discover how innovation and sustainability can change the world ? https://ow.ly/mucA50QkB5w	5	0	0	1	39	15,38 %
Dec 18.	11:58	Merry Christmas from the NOVASOIL project team.	5	0	0	5	45	22,22 %
Dec 14.	13:40	Report mapping existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models <i>Are incentives enough for the health of European soil?</i> https://ow.ly/Sht450QjTr	7	0	3	9	174	10,92 %
Dec 12.	09:14	We are currently at the NOVASOIL project's "Soil Health for a Sustainable Future" event. There are already over 140 participants! https://ow.ly/bMPZ50QhMOM	5	0	2	10	111	15,32 %
Dec 05.	12:55	Today we celebrate World Soil Day ! Discover the amazing world beneath your feet and get involved in taking care of our precious earth. https://ow.ly/4sre50Qfta9	6	0	1	0	50	14 %
Nov 30.	11:13	Baseline conceptual framework. I want to give you an exciting insight into the NOVASOIL project, which is revolutionizing how we approach soil health and sustainable management. https://ow.ly/XCZb50QcQ4l	6	0	1	5	76	15,79 %
Nov 29.	09:29	Register: NOVASOIL Online Event: Soil Health for a Sustainable Future - DAYS	2	0	0	1	62	4,84 %

Nov 24.	08:33	Soil regeneration and ecosystem health: A transformative journey https://ow.ly/CsiK50QaV0I	2	0	0	1	57	5,26 %
Nov 22.	08:35	Congratulations to our colleague Félix González, who has been selected as a finalist in the Mission Soil photography competition, which will be held in Madrid from 21 to 23 November 2023.	4	0	1	1	38	15,79 %
Nov 16.	14:04	Unraveling the tapestry of the earth: The profound effects of climate change on soil health - novasoil https://ow.ly/lCPF50Q8kiQ	2	0	0	0	21	9,52 %
Nov 14.	12:16	Identifying the threats beneath our feet. soil containing ...a risk to human health or the environment 🧠 https://ow.ly/cSAq50Q7nxR	2	0	0	0	25	8 %
Nov 13.	11:17	SECRETS UNDERGROUND Soil fertility refers to the ability of the soil to provide the essential nutrients required by plants for optimal growth	3	0	0	5	50	16 %
Nov 07.	11:45	A sustainable alternative for agriculture Fertilizers are used to enrich soil and provide essential nutrients for plant growth. but... https://ow.ly/7zul50Q4XGm	2	0	1	0	30	10 %
Nov 06.	13:19	The importance of soil conservation https://ow.ly/1uJ250Q4wuS	3	0	0	1	38	10,53 %
Nov 02.	19:58	Dimitre Nikolov - New Bulgarian University	2	0	1	0	27	11,11 %
Nov 02.	10:23	Guidance on the interpretation of physical and chemical soil test results. 🧠 https://ow.ly/pbmM50Q3nWU	1	0	1	0	34	5,88 %
Nov 01.	11:23	A Farmer's Perspective: Justifying the Causes of Soil Degradation https://ow.ly/2Ab550Q2XWS	3	0	1	0	42	9,52 %
Oct 31.	17:22	Benefits of healthy soil The quality and health of soils play a critical role in the sustainability of agriculture and the health of the natural environment https://ow.ly/bvFq50Q2KeC	4	0	1	0	99	5,05 %
Oct 30.	09:55	Your participation is important for NOVASOIL project 🏠 🧠 🏠 https://lnkd.in/eUNu4pbM	2	0	1	1	104	3,85 %
Oct 27.	10:06	Fabian Frick is a researcher at Technische Universität München researching on a project to develop and scale up business models for promoting soil health in different contexts. https://lnkd.in/gvBqEJTr https://lnkd.in/eFuyFZSy	4	0	0	0	69	5,8 %
Oct 24.	07:12	The second preliminary days of the NOVASOIL project continue today.	6	0	0	41	149	31,54 %

Oct 19.	17:58	Soil degradation and health highlighted at World Food Forum 2023 https://ow.ly/946350PYJyM	1	0	1	1	39	7,69 %
Oct 18.	10:26	Some of the news is not encouraging at all. 'THE COUNTRY IS BECOMING A DESERT' : DROUGHT STRUCK SPAIN IS RUNNING OUT OF WATER https://ow.ly/6Pr550PY3lt	3	0	1	2	58	10,34 %
Oct 17.	19:12	Do you think this Financial Times publication is true? https://ow.ly/6IUz50PXS5P	0	0	1	2	54	5,56 %
Oct 17.	11:01	10 Recommendations for Maintaining Healthy Soil	4	0	0	3	88	7,95 %
Oct 15.	09:21	International Rural Women's Day celebrates and recognizes the vital role of women in rural areas and their contributions to their communities and the world	3	0	0	0	63	4,76 %
Sep 26.	07:51	https://lnkd.in/dD6SaqRP	0	0	0	0	32	0 %
Sep 26.	07:51	https://lnkd.in/dxQFmWkP	1	0	0	0	36	2,78 %
Sep 12.	12:37	Soil health for all https://lnkd.in/dwm2fc-7	3	0	1	0	43	9,3 %
Sep 07.	10:33	The main objective is the research, development, improvement and implementation of new practices that will improve air quality and ultimately contribute to the well-being of the world's population.	1	0	0	0	44	2,27 %
Jul 26.	06:53	The components of the NOVASOIL project would like to celebrate the International Day for the Conservation of Mangroves 2023 with you. https://ow.ly/S6IQ50Plq6P	1	0	0	0	53	1,89 %
Jul 14.	12:07	Founded in 1918, the WUR specializes in areas related to agriculture, food, environment and sustainability. https://lnkd.in/eVXnnc4B	1	0	0	1	56	3,57 %
Jul 12.	09:32	Unlocking private investment in soil carbon in England Today we would like to share with you a publication developed by our colleagues at the University of Leeds https://ow.ly/7zOF50P9hjP	1	0	1	2	25	16 %
Jul 07.	10:01	Today is International Soil Conservation Day, and we are committed to raising awareness of the vital need to preserve the health of our precious soil.	1	0	0	0	15	6,67 %
Jul 07.	09:27	Istituto Delta Ecologia Applicata S.r.l. is a company created as a Spin-Off of the University of Ferrara. It was founded in 2001 by a group of researchers from the Department of Biology.	0	0	0	0	20	0 %
Jul 05.	10:13	Eco-schemes: a key tool for sustainable agriculture in the EU	1	0	0	2	30	10 %

		https://ow.ly/Fw5650P3My3						
Jun 27,	07:42	The invisible life under our feet. World Microbiome Day https://lnkd.in/eDgSUM74	0	0	1	0	21	4,76 %
Jun 23,	06:44	Our goal is to promote sustainable development, cooperation, and knowledge exchange in the agricultural sector.	1	0	0	0	37	2,7 %
Jun 17,	12:32	(Sin descripción)	0	0	0	0	6	0 %
Jun 16,	11:24	Founded in 1939, the CNR is France's leading scientific research organization and conducts research in a wide range of scientific disciplines, including soils.	1	0	1	0	33	6,06 %
Jun 05,	18:22	"The health of the soil is the foundation of all life on this planet, and just as we take care of our bodies, we must take care of the earth that sustains us." - Jane Goodall http://ow.ly/a4Ki50OG2C5	0	0	0	0	53	0 %
Jun 04,	16:44	(Sin descripción)	0	0	0	1	40	2,5 %
Jun 02,	07:48	Founded in 1479, Københavns Universitet is Denmark's oldest university. It is an internationally recognised research institution. http://ow.ly/sle550OC1zf	0	0	0	1	36	2,78 %
Jun 01,	08:44	Last week's Plenary meeting demonstrated the spectacular performance of these researchers. Thank you all for your commitment. https://lnkd.in/eFuyFZSy	6	0	2	6	66	21,21 %
May 31,	19:29	Case study on ecosystem services provided by forests in Southern Italy https://lnkd.in/eyB-kdff	1	0	2	0	34	8,82 %
May 26,	07:08	Founded in 1939, the CNRS is France's largest scientific research agency, dedicated to advancing knowledge in a wide range of scientific disciplines. http://ow.ly/xTrl50OxmOx	1	0	0	2	40	7,5 %
May 15,	17:31	Next week we will hold the preliminary meeting of the NOVASOIL project.	7	0	2	1	94	10,64 %
May 12,	09:12	The University of Leeds was founded in 1874 as the Yorkshire College of Science. Over the years, it has developed a strong track record in soil science and has carried out pioneering research in several soil-related areas. https://lnkd.in/eFuyFZSy	0	0	0	2	55	3,64 %

May 05.	12:09	The New University of Bulgaria (founded in 1991) is another partner of the NOVASOIL project that brings high value to the project. https://lnkd.in/eVXnnc4B	0	0	0	1	39	2,56 %
Apr 25.	06:57	Zemnieku Saeima has been working for the interests of farmers and rural development in Latvia since 1989. http://ow.ly/maQr50NR6NA	0	0	0	0	40	0 %
Apr 22.	08:45	"The Earth is poetry in motion, a masterpiece deserving of our care." - Amit Ray	0	0	0	0	20	0 %
Apr 19.	12:44	Today we would like to start by introducing the partners that make up this great NOVASOIL consortium. We start with ZALF. http://ow.ly/v63g50NMLJO	0	0	0	0	21	0 %
Apr 17.	08:33	What role do soils play in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals? In this post, we discuss the benefits of soil health in the SDGs.	1	0	0	0	25	4 %
Apr 04.	12:22	<big> Regenerative agriculture: a cost-effective and sustainable solution for the agricultural sector </big> http://ow.ly/nPvo50NzKcM	1	0	0	0	40	2,5 %
Mar 31.	10:09	How sustainable agriculture is improving soil health and transforming the food industry http://ow.ly/c5fq50NwUIR	2	0	0	2	45	8,89 %
Mar 27.	08:23	The importance of stakeholder participation in environmental and agricultural projects in Europe http://ow.ly/tKBi50Nsll4	1	0	0	1	38	5,26 %
Mar 13.	10:05	Over 250 signatories, including farmers, scientists, startups, retail, finance, civil society, health and water associations, govt. associations, and citizens, support an ambitious #SoilHealthLaw in an open letter to the European Commission.	5	0	0	3	50	16 %
Mar 09.	11:14	New NOVASOIL project sheets to consult. What is the value of an organic vineyard? http://ow.ly/tjOQ50NcYFi	3	0	2	0	28	17,86 %
Mar 03.	11:17	The leaflets of the NOVASOIL project case studies are now available. http://ow.ly/blil50N82rM	2	0	0	0	22	9,09 %
Mar 02.	10:06	The brochure with the case study of integrated production in Mediterranean olive groves is now available. http://ow.ly/eSLz50N6Shq	2	0	0	0	15	13,33 %
Feb 27.	13:04	We share with you the brochure with the first of the TUM case studies on the NOVASOIL project. (DE language). http://ow.ly/NOea50N3reF	1	0	0	1	26	7,69 %

Feb 27.	12:01	TUM – Bodenfruchtbarkeitsfonds NOVASOIL https://lnkd.in/erPVUDKu	0	0	1	1	40	5 %
Feb 27.	09:24	Zemnieku Saeima - novasoil https://lnkd.in/eXV-uZrK	0	0	0	0	23	0 %
Feb 10.	10:17	We are holding the Multiplier Event of the NOVASOIL project in Spain. https://lnkd.in/eFuyFZSy	4	0	2	2	53	15,09 %
Jan 24.	12:05	The POLYFACE case study for soil regeneration http://ow.ly/4GnX50MyJpm	3	0	0	1	51	7,84 %
Jan 13.	09:19	Inscrivez-vous au premier événement du projet NOVASOIL qui aura lieu le 3 février. https://lnkd.in/eFSYZe-g	2	0	2	2	39	15,38 %
Dec 23.	12:37	(Sin descripción)	0	0	0	0	23	0 %
Dec 23.	12:36	Both the web platform of the NOVASOIL project and the blog have been created with the aim of informing the community of material related to the objectives of the project.	4	0	0	4	56	14,29 %

5 Acknowledgment

The authors thank the European Union for funding from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement GA 101091268. The views expressed in this document are those of the authors. The Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

